

InterAcción y Perspectiv

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X
D.L. pp 201002Z43506

Julio-septiembre 2024
Vol. 14 No. 2

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

Interacción y Perspectiva
Revista de Trabajo Social
Vol. 14 N°2 386-398 pp.
Julio-septiembre

Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506
ISSN 2244-808X
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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

La influencia de las tecnologías de la información y la comunicación en el desarrollo de las estructuras sociales y políticas de la sociedad red

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10909782>

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Resumen

El objetivo del estudio es analizar la transformación de las estructuras sociopolíticas de la sociedad red, teniendo en cuenta la influencia de los procesos de globalización y el desarrollo de las tecnologías de la información y la comunicación. Dado que vivimos en una sociedad interconectada donde las tecnologías de la información y la comunicación desempeñan un papel clave, es importante examinar cómo estos factores configuran el panorama sociopolítico. Para lograr este objetivo, es necesario estudiar la relación entre las estructuras sociales y políticas, los procesos de globalización y el desarrollo de las tecnologías de la información y la comunicación. Se utilizaron los siguientes métodos: abstracción, deducción, sistematización y generalización. Se ha determinado que el surgimiento de una sociedad en red provoca una reestructuración de las instituciones sociopolíticas, lo que conduce al surgimiento de nuevas estructuras y determina las características específicas del funcionamiento de las redes sociopolíticas en el contexto de la globalización. Se analiza la influencia de las instituciones sociales en la digitalización. En 2022 se llevó a cabo en Ucrania un estudio sobre la representación de los intereses sociales a nivel de red. Se investiga la transformación de la influencia de las redes de información y comunicación en el desarrollo de las estructuras sociopolíticas de la sociedad red y la formación de enfoques para la interacción del aparato político con los ciudadanos.

Palabras clave: grupos sociales, sociedad red, estructuras sociopolíticas, información, comunicación, organización

Abstract

The influence of information and communication technologies on the development of social and political structures of the network society

The purpose of the study is to analyze the transformation of the socio-political structures of the network society, taking into account the influence of globalization processes and the development of information and communication technologies. Since we live in a networked society where information and communication technologies play a key role, it is important to examine how these factors shape the socio-political landscape. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to study the relationship between social and political structures, globalization processes and the development of information and communication technologies. We used the following methods: abstraction, deduction,

systematization and generalization. It has been determined that the emergence of a network society causes a restructuring of socio-political institutions, which leads to the emergence of new structures and determines the specifics of the functioning of socio-political networks in the context of globalization. The influence of social institutions on digitalization is analyzed. The study of the representation of social interests at the network level was conducted in Ukraine in 2022. The transformation of the influence of information and communication networks on the development of socio-political structures of the network society and the formation of approaches to the interaction of the political apparatus with citizens is investigated.

Keywords: social groups, network society, socio-political structures, information, communication, organization.

Recibido: 26/12/2023 Aceptado: 12/02/2024

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1. Introduction

The concept of a networked society based on the network methodology has various implementation options that can lead to both proper functioning and collapse of socio-economic systems. In this regard, the issue of joining global development networks and adopting the established rules of interaction is becoming relevant for most countries.

It is worth noting that the network organization of society has existed for a long time, but the growth of the internal interconnectedness of the world system, which has become an effective catalyst for the transformational development of the modern world, has provided more opportunities for the formation of network relations. This approach adequately responds to internal and external challenges, which in turn leads to optimization of the processes of establishing links between participants in global structures.

An important challenge of today is to study the impact of communication relations and information flows on the transformation of political structures, taking into account the dynamic development of the modern environment. However, the problem of defining the essence and specifics of the functioning of the network society for the methodology

of modern science is not new. Some aspects of this problem are not sufficiently covered in modern research approaches. For example, the genesis of political structures as a component of the network society in the context of the development of information and communication technologies is not sufficiently disclosed. Therefore, the problem of analyzing the impact of information and communication technologies on the structures of the network society is of great practical importance.

Objectives is the process of transformation of the political structures of the network society, taking into account the impact of globalization processes and the development of information and communication technologies.

2. Literature review

In the context of globalization, the networked society represents a new form of world organization that can self-organize, restructure, and self-regulate. It is a system that is constantly expanding, as it penetrates all societies with different intensities and ways. Thus, the network society is understood as a structured objective reality.

Within the framework of the study of the network society, the analysis of political processes has become an integral component, although not all researchers working in this area use structural analysis tools to study such phenomena as relations between states and social groups within states or global dependencies in political structures at the level of the world system. Particular attention should be paid to M. Castells, who studied the peculiarities of the formation of a network society in the context of globalization. Also worth noting are the works of D. Nook, M. Mizruchi, A. Mager and other researchers. M. Mizruchi emphasizes that one of the promising areas in network analysis is the study of the power structure and the study of relations between corporations and the state. This creates a natural connection between political economy and network analysis, which echoes the ideas of M. Castells and other network analysts.

3. Results and discussion

The formation of a network society is a necessary response to the challenges of globalization, characterized by the growing influence of information technologies and cultural movements, which, in turn, is a key factor in the formation of the structure of interchangeable global networks that are gradually changing the established social reality. M. Castells noted that the network society is "the social structure of our century, the age of information, just as industrial society was the social structure of the industrial age. It is a global social structure, and therefore it applies to all societies. Despite institutional and cultural diversity, the global network society is characterized by a fundamental common core. Not every society or every segment of every society is

included in this core. However, the logic of networks means that they include and exclude at the same time" (Castells, 2023).

It is important to analyze and characterize the processes of formation of the network society as a component of the socio-economic system in the context of globalization. According to M. Castells (Castells, 2000), since the early 70s, three important and independent processes have been taking place in parallel: the information technology revolution, the development of cultural and social movements of the 60s and 70s, and the crisis that led to the restructuring of two socio-economic systems - capitalism and ethicism. These processes resulted in the emergence of a network society. Nowadays, ethicism and capitalism cannot adapt to the requirements of globalization, which leads to economic conflicts and loss of political control in various spheres of society.

M. Castells postulated that the formation of a network society is inherent in countries with capitalist economies (Castells, 2000). However, this economy is characterized by a new paradigm - knowledge and information are the driving force of competitiveness in the global space (Fuchs, 2009, Smart, 2000).

To meet the demands of the modern world, both people and countries must adopt a network approach to interaction. A network, in turn, is an organizational structure that describes the interaction between objects that are united by various forms of connections based on human interaction. This interaction is based on the realization of common interests, regardless of geopolitical factors. This leads to relevant socio-political, cultural and historical changes in the modern world.

Various research approaches to the emergence of the network society trace a technological paradigm that determines that its emergence is associated with the development of microelectronics, genetic engineering, and information and communication technologies, as well as with industrial and post-industrial types of social development. However, this is not the only factor. A conceptual difference in the formation of the network society is the emergence of information technology networks that have emerged as a result of industrial and technological development.

Modern information technologies are a key factor in the formation of interaction structures that form global networks. These networks, including media, mobile communications, and the Internet, have become horizontal and vertical forms of global communication in the early twenty-first century. Networked forms of social organization provide flexibility in the activities of people, structures, and countries. However, these forms require constant adaptation to new conditions of social development and needs. Each country determines its own criteria for the formation of relevant networks in a world where there are no rules for organizing global life.

The development of information and communication technologies involves the creation of information structures that help develop educational, scientific and cultural infrastructure through appropriate forms of interaction between global actors. This requires standardization of service quality and modernization of the telecommunications

infrastructure, which helps to reduce the gap in information and economic development between countries.

Today, networked forms of information interaction are transforming social reality, which leads to changes in the functioning of the main spheres of life and forms of relations between people. The information basis of social development, according to M. Castells, is based on the ideology of informationism, which determines the ways and directions of social evolution.

Internet technologies play an important role in the formation of information structures. These technologies allow establishing many direct contacts, such as international, personal, business, and cultural networks, removing space and time constraints. Thanks to Internet technologies, new information structures are being formed, which are the basis for network interaction, providing quick solutions to social problems.

In the context of the network society, as O. Zernetska notes, communication is becoming a new importance for society and the individual, which leads to a civilizational revolution at this stage of human development (Zernetska, 2019).

In a world where all spheres of life depend on the information space and global networks, the feasibility of joining them and fully establishing network connections are becoming extremely important issues for countries around the world. Information and communication technologies need to be modernized in order to become part of the global information network. The formation of clearly defined information centers-networks that set standards for information technologies and develop strategies for their development is a fundamental feature of the impact of modern globalization processes. These information centers-networks ensure the transfer of information and technologies to the backward periphery, forming appropriate information structures. The network society, which emerges as a result of the establishment of information and communication interaction, creates infrastructures that are entirely dependent on the factor of information and technological development of a particular network.

Networks unite various information structures that are forms of social organization. The development of information technologies allows to strengthen the essence and functionality of these structures. The current role of information structures in the respective networks determines their strategic and tactical importance, as they effectively form network relations.

To fully understand the relationship between the digitalization process and governance, it is necessary to conduct a systematic and historical analysis of the concepts, narratives, and belief systems that influence this context. Critical conceptual analysis, typically associated with political theory, history, or sociology, plays an important role in such a study. Its inclusion in digitalization studies promises significant progress in two ways.

“On the one hand, analyzing concepts, narratives, and belief systems will provide an overview of the competing representations of the networked society” (August, 2022:

314) that we face in policy terms. By historicizing these representations, we will be able to remove the naturalness of the rationalities underlying the proposed governance models. On the other hand, a critical analysis of metaphors and narratives in discussions about digitalization will also contribute to the methodological accuracy of the study of the digitalization of the political structures of the network society.

The study of the impact of communication methods on political and social development, especially in the context of the rapid development of information and communication technologies, is of great importance. In the twentieth century, television has already proved its effectiveness as a channel for broadcasting mass socio-political influence (McLuhan, 1967). The modern world is characterized by the expansion of electronic technologies as a means of supporting social communications. Network structures emerging in connection with the globalization of society create a new social morphology. Network relations are penetrating the political system to the extent that they are seen as a key tool for identifying citizens, organizing and coordinating political participation of different segments of the population.

This necessitates further research into the impact of network relations on political processes and the development of society. Sociologists, political scientists, and other researchers are actively studying these processes to understand what changes new communication technologies and network structures bring and how they affect politics and human behavior in the modern world.

The emergence of a network society causes the restructuring of political institutions, which leads to the emergence of new political structures and determines the specifics of the functioning of political networks in the context of globalization. Political structures that are united in political networks form relations between political actors that ensure political decision-making. At the same time, D. Clarke once postulated the principles of renouncing political jurisdiction over the Internet, appealing to the fact that the Internet is a decentralized and deterritorialized set of peer-to-peer networks. Consequently, the Internet is inherent in self-regulation and should be free from centralized governance, which includes representative democratic institutions (Pohle J., & Thorsten T., 2019).

A. Toffler (Toffler, 1980) emphasizes the importance of media interactivity, which is increasing due to the introduction of new network technologies. He predicts that information and knowledge will become the main resources of power by the end of the 21st century. This suggests that changes in communication methods have a major impact on the distribution of power in society.

Changes in communication methods not only transmit information, but also affect people's values and consciousness. The individual and political consciousness of citizens is changing under the influence of new communication methods, which can lead to a revision of social values.

In Deutsch's theory (Deutsch, 1963), the political system is viewed as a complex network of information flows and communication relations, where feedback plays an important role. The effectiveness of a political system depends on the quality and

quantity of incoming information, as well as the way it is processed, transmitted and stored.

These guidelines emphasize the interrelationship between communication networks, the distribution of power, and the functioning of the political system. The development of new communication methods affects these processes and can have significant consequences for society as a whole.

Information exchange forms the basic prerequisites for the sustainable formation of the political system, which is characterized by three main types of communication: personal, informal communication; communication through organizations; and communication through the media. The overall goal of political communication is interaction between political actors through the exchange of information in the process of struggle for power, exercise of power or retention of power. This goal is realized through the targeted transmission and selective perception of information.

Today, the global infrastructure of electronic means of collecting, storing, processing and transmitting information is striking in its scope of influence in the scale of its impact on the system of social and political relations. The first wave of information (from the late nineteenth century to the 1950s) had no direct impact on the political life of society. The second wave actually created a new social reality that required completely new types of organization, behavior, motivation, and ethics.

Receiving information is perceived by the mass consciousness as the only reliable way to development, as a mechanism of social regulation.

The information and communication network of a political system, according to Deutsch, includes: services for receiving information, evaluating and selecting information, making decisions, implementing decisions, and feedback (Deutsch, 1963). At the first stage, external and internal information is collected through information services and public opinion centers; this information does not have a strict correlation with further public policy goals. At this stage, the incoming data is selected, systematized, initially analyzed and coded. After evaluation and processing, the selected information is further transformed in accordance with the dominant values, norms, stereotypes, and preferences of the ruling elite.

The state as a subject of public administration mobilizes the political system through information flows of regulation and communication interactions between the system and the social environment, as well as between individual blocks within the system. Government decisions are made after receiving a general assessment of the current political situation's compliance with the main goals and objectives of the political situation for compliance with the main goals and objectives of state policy. Feedback in the information and communication network plays a stabilizing role. The "executors" not only implement the decisions made, but also inform about the results of the implementation of decisions and the state of the system as a whole. Thus, new information through the feedback mechanism reaches the "input" and brings the entire system to a new round of functioning.

The communication network of the political system transmits three main types of messages: technological data related to establishing and maintaining contacts between the elements of the political system; informative data that convey the main semantic content of the transmitted message; and motivational appeals that cause a desire or understanding of the need for certain actions in accordance with the content of the received information (Deutsch, 1969, p. 13).

Deutsch's information and communication model allows us to assess the effectiveness of political systems. However, within this approach, the problem of the effectiveness of interaction between the communicator and the recipient is reduced to only studying various channels, ways and methods of information transmission, leaving out the processes of perception and mutual behavior of individuals.

The information network implies not only the depersonalization of subjects, but also the ability of citizens to choose the information they need. The energy of a massive, active, and politically functioning public sphere should not be ignored both in the information and communication space of virtual reality and in real historical space and time.

The public should not be seen as a passive object of political influence. It is selective about all types of external influence, accepting and assimilating some and rejecting others. Objectively good information materials may turn out to be much less effective in practice than communicators and owners of mass media systems expect. As a result, instead of forming beliefs, the material will serve to overly reinforce existing views, attitudes, and moods that encourage action.

M. Kaufmann and J. Jeandesboz (Kaufmann M., & Jeandesboz J., 2017) and S. Berg (Berg, S, Niklas R, & Thorsten T., 2020) note that the issue of digitalization of society should be considered taking into account accessibility for political decisions.

A study of the impact of democratic institutions on digitalization (Mager, A., and Katzenbach C., 2021) showed that the development and social functioning of digital technologies depends on the legal framework established by politics.

The study of E. Laumann and D. Knoke (Laumann EO, and Knoke D., 1987) on the inter-organizational network of national politics in Washington is an illustrative example of empirical research. They argued that much of the government in the United States was under the influence of narrow and largely autonomous elites. These elites do not directly lead the country because their actions are inconsistent with each other on various issues (Mizruchi, 1992).

However, E. Laumann and D. Knoke emphasize the role of latent social ties in policy-making between leaders of different network organizations interested in solving specific issues (Fischer, 2013). D. Knoke (1994) considers network analysis at the macro-theoretical level, exploring the relations of influence (exchange of information) and domination (exchange of material sanctions) and demonstrating how ties between

businessmen contribute to the communication of corporate class interests to the public domain (Marsh, D. and Smith, M., 2000).

E. Voinova noted in her work (Voinova, 2021) that new forms of communication, especially in the context of the Internet and web networks, cause changes in social interaction, including the political sphere. This is supported by the indication that new models of social interaction, including political interaction, are emerging as a result of the development of the Internet. Differentiation and variability of information flows are becoming special characteristics of new forms of communication. A variety of information sources and wide access to it contribute to demassification, i.e., less control over information flows. This allows more people to express their opinions and engage in political communication. In addition, the processes of individualization of political communication are becoming more prominent, as people can choose the information that meets their interests and views.

These changes in political communication reflect the impact of new technologies and can have a significant impact on the political sphere. With the help of new forms of communication, citizens can communicate more, exchange information and express their views, leading to changes in political debate and the formation of new political models of interaction.

The rapidly growing development and popularity of blogs, video blogs, podcasts, streaming, and other forms of interactive communication on the Internet is creating a new system of global, horizontal communication networks that, for the first time in history, allow people to communicate with each other without going through the channels created by the institutions of society for socialized communication (Castells, 2006, p. 13). Communication on the Internet is mass communication because it is distributed globally and potentially covers the entire planet. But it is also self-directed, as it is often initiated by individuals and groups. However, this does not mean instant emancipation for everyone on the Internet. The Internet consists of both an oligopolistic business-multimedia system that controls an increasingly inclusive hypertext and an explosion of horizontal networks of autonomous local and global communication. autonomous local and global communication. Socialized communication is a world of diversified messages that recombine themselves in electronic hypertext and are processed by the mind through increasingly autonomous information sources.

The modern concept of smart government is based on a new platform of Smart Networks. The Smart Networks platform involves the use of communication networks to manage various types of systems (Voronkova, et al., 2022).

To facilitate the establishment and development of global-local ties in the modern network society, the state actively encourages the establishment of a comprehensive process of networking. This process involves regional and local authorities, various non-governmental organizations and business structures. Governance is no longer limited to nation-states, but functions within a network of political institutions and private actors. These actors collectively share sovereignty and adapt to the changing geopolitical ecosystem (Castells, 2006, p. 16).

The digital technology transformation of the industrial revolution from 4G to 5G is characterized by the dominance of revolutionary digital-based production methods such as the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, and Big Data. Analyzing the determinants of social development, V. Voronkova et al. identify the main driving forces of socio-economic progress: the development of human resources based on artificial intelligence, "intelligent production", which involves managing production and logistics on an enterprise scale, facilitating human-computer interaction, as well as the introduction of 3D technologies in production processes and the transition to 5G technology, which will increase the speed of data transmission and enable the simultaneous connection of more devices.

The development of a science and technology-oriented workforce is crucial for countries to take advantage of digital transformation processes (Voronkova et al., 2023).

Considering the role of education in the cognitive development of society as a factor of digital transformation, a team of scientists (Nikitenko et al., 2022) conclude that the emergence of the digital and knowledge economy has transformed human nature and work, leading to the emergence of a cognitive society and the emergence of the "digital human". The technological revolution has allowed people to connect online and has fostered a network effect that allows people to work and earn income remotely. However, digital transformation also brings challenges, such as cybercrime and data security issues.

It is worth noting that according to the «E-Government Survey 2022» (The United Nations, 2022), Ukraine has risen from 82nd place to 46th in 5 years, which indicates a positive trend in the development of e-government in Ukraine. The growth of the country's position from 82nd to 69th place in two years is an important indicator. This means that Ukraine is making some efforts to implement and develop e-government.

"According to a study by Kantar, a market research company, almost 84% of smartphone owners in Ukraine use "Diia" today." (Rating of mobile applications: 84% of smartphone owners in Ukraine use the "Diia" app, 2022).

According to the analytical report "Opinions and Views of the Ukrainian Population on State Electronic Services," the level of use of state electronic services in Ukraine continues to grow - in 2022, 63% of Ukrainians used state electronic services, compared to 60% in 2021 and 53% in 2020 (Analytical report on the «Opinions and views of the Ukrainian population regarding state electronic services», 2022).

Ukraine's transition from a group with a high e-government development index to a group with a very high index, and becoming one of 60 countries with this status, is also an important achievement. This indicates certain improvements in the use of technology and electronic services in public administration in Ukraine.

It is worth noting that these achievements can have a positive impact on the accessibility of services for citizens, the efficiency of government processes, and the transparency and openness of the government. The development of e-governance

improves communication between the government and citizens, ensures greater public participation in decision-making processes, and promotes trust in the government.

4. Conclusions

Thus, the process of transformation of political structures under the influence of information and communication technologies in a network society has its own peculiarities. In the modern world, the process of transformation of political structures is taking place due to the representation of social interests at the level of macro networks. This change occurs through the expression of social demands, the unification of social requirements and political decision-making. Much attention is paid to open and free communication between different networks and within each network, which helps to improve the feedback between the government and citizens. Political relations are mediated by information networks, and the main emphasis is shifting from maintaining the dominant role of public authorities to finding optimal forms of interaction aimed at protecting the rights of citizens when formulating the political interests of social networks and discussing political issues.

In the process of formation of political structures of the network society, new opportunities for communication and interaction, development of the digital state, transformation of bureaucratic political structures into effective interaction between the state and network communities are opening up. It seems expedient to further comprehensively analyze the trends in the development of network society structures, which will make it possible to predict the development of social institutions in the context of globalization.

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